

Mannich reactions on spiro-*s*-tetrazines and their antibacterial and antifungal activities

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Abstract : A number of novel Mannich bases from spiro-*s*-tetrazines **2** have been synthesized. The reaction of a tetraazaspiroalkanes **2** underwent Mannich reaction in two different routes to afford identical target molecule **6** and **7**. Spiro-*s*-tetrazines **2** on cyclocondensation with chloroacetic acid and sodium acetate in method A furnished the corresponding thiazolidinones **3** which on subsequent Mannich reaction with formaldehyde, 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone and 1,3-diphenylthiobarbituric acid yielded Mannich bases **6** and **7**, respectively in moderate to good yield. In an alternative method B the spiro-*s*-tetrazines **2**, formed Mannich bases **4** and **5** which after final installation of thiazolidinone moiety produced the same target compounds **6** and **7**. The subsequent exocyclic olefinic linkage was made on thiazolidinone units of the same Mannich bases **6** and **7** on reaction with benzaldehyde to form the benzylidene compounds **8** and **9**. Some of the compounds were screened for their biological activities against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. cirroflagellosus*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans*.

Keywords : Mannich bases, spiro-*s*-tetrazines, Mannich reaction, 1,3-diphenylthiobarbituric acid, thiazolidinone, benzylidene.

Introduction

The fungicidal and bactericidal activities¹ of some *s*-tetrazine derivatives are well documented. Certain thiazolidin-4-one derivatives are found to have potential pharmaceutical activities²⁻⁴. A number of thiobarbiturate derivatives are reported to exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activities, viz. anticonvulsant⁵, anaesthetic⁶, sedative and hypnotic⁷⁻⁹ activities. In addition, a good number of nitrogen containing spiroheterocycles have been reported to display narcotic¹⁰, bactericidal¹¹⁻¹⁵, antitumor^{16,17}, antibiotic^{18,19}, anticancer²⁰ and antidiabetes²¹ properties. In view of the application potentials of the aforesaid heterocycles, we report herein the synthesis of novel Mannich bases on reaction of different spiro-*s*-tetrazine derivatives **2a-d** with thiazolidinone and barbiturate moieties. The synthesis of these new class of Mannich bases were efficiently carried out by exploiting the secondary amine group linked to spiro carbon using standard Mannich reaction. Some of the Mannich bases

were screened for their antimicrobial activities against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. cirroflagellosus*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans*.

Results and discussion

Mannich reaction of spiro-*s*-tetrazines is reported here for the first time. The target compounds **6** and **7** formed by two different methods are found to be same in all respects of their physical, analytical and spectral properties. The spiro-*s*-tetrazines **2a-d** are prepared by cyclocondensation of various cycloalkanones with thiocarbohydrazides as per the reported procedure by Lamon²² (Scheme 1). The tetrazine derivatives **2** in method A, underwent cyclocondensation with chloroacetic acid in anhydrous ethanolic sodium acetate to form thiazolidinone derivatives **3a-d** as reported earlier²³.

The thiazolidinone derivative **3** underwent Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and active methylene compounds like 2-(*N*-phenyl)imino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone

and 1,3-diphenyl thiobarbituric acid to form Mannich bases **6a-d** and **7a-d**, respectively. In the IR spectrum of the

Mannich base **6c**, an additional carbonyl stretching frequency at 1722 cm^{-1} and disappearance of the NH stretching frequency ensured the insertion of two thiazolidinone moieties at 1 and 5 positions through a methylene group. In PMR spectra, a triplet at $\delta\ 3.92$ ($J\ 7.2\ \text{Hz}$) ppm and a doublet at $\delta\ 4.21$ ($J\ 7.2\ \text{Hz}$) ppm along with a sharp singlet at $\delta\ 3.76$ ppm correspond to two methine proton, four methylene protons of *N*-bonded 2-(thiazolidinonyl)-methyl group and two methylene protons of annulated thiazolidinone moiety, respectively. Two separate multiplets centred at $\delta\ 6.8\text{--}7.0$ and $\delta\ 7.1\text{--}7.7$ ppm correspond to eight *ortho* phenyl protons and twelve *meta* and *para* aromatic protons, respectively. The ^{13}C NMR spectra of the same compound gave sharp peaks at $\delta\ 173.38, 171.27, 147.89, 58.08, 48.2, 36.88$ for carbonyl carbon, imino carbon, spiro carbon, methylene carbon and methine carbon, respectively. The peaks for 2,7-carbons, 3,6-carbons and 4,5-carbons of the cycloheptyl unit observed at $\delta\ 30.10, 27.5, 24.23$, respectively are correspond to the proposed structure **6c**.

(i) ClCH_2COOH , NaOAc/AcOH ; (ii) HCHO ; (iii) PhCHO

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Zenith apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer using KBr disc. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC 300 MHz NMR spectrometer and were obtained in CDCl₃. The % of C, H, N were determined by Flash-2000 organic elemental analyser. Purity of the products were checked by TLC, using silica gel "G" (BDH) and hexane-ethyl acetate as eluent. 1,3-Diphenylthiourea²⁴ and 2-(*N*-phenyl)imino, 3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone²⁵ were prepared as per reported procedure.

General procedure for preparation of spiro-s-tetrazine (3) :

A mixture of the compound **2** (0.01 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.01 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 5 h. The resultant solution was concentrated, cooled and kept overnight. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from rectified spirit to give **3**.

*General procedure for preparation of thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-s-tetrazines (6 or 7) :*

Method-A :

A mixture of compound **3** (0.0025 mol), formaldehyde (0.005 mol) and thiazolidinone derivative/1,3-diphenylthiobarbituric acid (0.005 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid on a hot plate for 4 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured into ice cold water. The solid that separated was filtered and recrystallised from rectified spirit.

Characterization data of compound **6c** and **7c** are given below.

Compound 6c : Yield (82%), m.p 173 °C; IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : ν 3049, 2952, 1738, 1722 (C=O), 1591 (C=N), 759 (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.48–1.56 (8H, m, 4 × CH₂), 2.52–2.63 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂), 3.76 (2H, s, *J* 7.2 Hz, S-CH₂-CO-), 3.92 (2H, t, -S-CH-CO-), 4.21 (4H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, N-CH₂-), 6.8–7.0 (8H, m, *o*-phenyl protons), 7.1–7.7 (12H, m, *m,p*-phenyl protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 24.23, 27.5, 30.10, 32.74 (thiazolidinone S-CH₂-CO-), 36.88 (S-CH-CO-), 48.2 (N-CH₂-), 58.08

(spiro-C), 127.8, 128.8, 129, 129.2, 130.23, 132.15, 134.5, 137.19, 147.89 (N=C-S), 153.88 (C=N), 171.27, 173.38 (C=O) (Found : C, 62.86; H, 4.58; N, 13.65; S, 11.88. Calcd. for C₄₂H₄₀N₈O₃S₃ : C, 63.00; H, 5.00; N, 14.00; S, 12.00%).

Compound 7c : Yield (64%), m.p 172 °C; IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : ν 3050, 2955, 1720 (C=O), 1690 (C=O), 1600 (C=N), 755 (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.45–1.53 (8H, m, 4 × CH₂), 2.50–2.59 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂), 3.63 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, -CH- of the ring), 3.75 (2H, s, S-CH₂-), 4.29 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, N-CH₂-), 6.9–7.2 (8H, m, *o*-phenyl protons), 7.3–7.7 (12H, m, *m,p*-phenyl protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 24.30, 27.48, 30.12, 32.71 (thiazolidinone -CH-), 35.71 (S-CH-CO-), 48.51 (N-CH₂-), 58.56 (spiro-C), 127.3, 128, 129.1, 129.22, 129.42, 130.17, 131.45, 134.5, 137.19, 147.90 (N=C-S), 162.60 (C=S), 171.35 (C=O), 177.30 (C=O) (Found : C, 61.55; H, 4.62; N, 12.67; S, 11.15. Calcd. for C₄₄H₄₀N₈O₅S₃ : C, 61.68; H, 4.67; N, 13.08; S, 11.21%).

Method-B :

General procedure for preparation of 1,2,4,5-tetraazaspiro-3-thione (4 or 5) :

A mixture of compound **2** (0.0025 mol), formaldehyde (0.005 mol) and thiazolidinone derivative/1,3-diphenylthiobarbituric acid (0.005 mol) in 10 mL glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a hot plate for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold water. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from rectified spirit.

Characterization data of compound **4c** and **5c** are given below.

Compound 4c : Yield (85%), m.p 170 °C; IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : ν 3240 (N-H), 3050, 2955, 1720 (C=O), 1613 (C=N), 772 (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.58–1.67 (8H, m, 4 × CH₂), 2.49–2.55 (4H, m, 2 × -CH₂-), 3.91 (2H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz, S-CH-), 4.29 (4H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz, N-CH₂-), 6.8–7.15 (8H, m, *o*-phenyl protons), 7.2–7.6 (12H, m, *m,p*-phenyl protons), 8.45–8.51 (2H, bs, 2 × NHCS); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 23.87, 27.50, 30.15, 37.18 (S-CH-CO-), 48.40 (N-CH₂-), 58.21 (spiro-C), 127.8, 128.8, 129.21, 129.52, 130.35, 130.58, 134.5, 136.89, 154.80 (C=N), 168.1 (C=S), 171.30 (C=O) (Found : C, 62.99;

H, 5.21; N, 14.70; S, 12.59. Calcd. for $C_{40}H_{40}N_8O_2S_3$: C, 63.16; H, 5.26; N, 14.74; S, 12.63%.

Compound 5c: Yield (65%), m.p 134 °C; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}): ν 3317 (N-H), 3049, 2952, 1687 (C=O), 1592 (C=N), 1230 (C=S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 1.54–1.63 (8H, m, 4 $\times$ CH_2), 2.46–2.53 (4H, m, 2 $\times$ CH_2), 3.60 (2H, t, J 7.3 Hz, S-CH-), 4.29 (4H, d, J 7.3 Hz, N- CH_2 -), 6.68–7.26 (8H, m, *o*-phenyl protons), 7.3–7.7 (12H, m, *m,p*-phenyl protons), 8.4–8.52 (2H, bs, 2 $\times$ NHCS); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 24.24, 27.48, 30.12, 36.88 (S-CH-CO-), 48.31 (N- CH_2), 58.45 (spiro-C), 127.78, 128.58, 129.2, 136.77, 168.8, 171.3 (C=S), 177.3 (C-O) (Found: C, 61.24; H, 4.35; N, 13.58; S, 11.55. Calcd. for $C_{42}H_{40}N_8O_4S_3$: C, 61.76; H, 4.90; N, 13.72; S, 11.76%).

The mixture of equimolar amount of compound 4/5 (0.0025 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.005 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a hot plate for 5 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured into ice cold water. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit.

The spectral data of product 6/7 obtained by Method-B is superimposable with that of Method-A.

General procedure for preparation of benzilidene derivatives of spiro thiazolo-s-tetrazine (8 or 9):

A solution of compound 6/7 (0.0025 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.0025 mol) in ethyl alcohol (5 mL) in presence of piperidine (3 drops) was refluxed for 5 h on water bath. The volume was reduced, cooled and poured into ice cold water. The solid thus separated was filtered, dried and subsequently crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

Characterization data of compound 8c and 9c are given below.

Compound 8c: Yield (62%); m.p 212 °C; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}): ν 3050, 2955, 1722 (C=O), 1712 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1593 (C=C), 755 (C-S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 1.48–1.60 (8H, m, 4 $\times$ CH_2), 2.52–2.56 (4H, m, 2 $\times$ CH_2), 3.87 (t, J 6.9 Hz, S-CH-), 4.20 (4H, d, J 6.9 Hz, 2 $\times$ N- CH_2 -), 7.0–7.77 (25H, m, phenyl protons), 8.0 (1H, s, *exo*-olephenic proton); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 24.30, 27.48, 30.12, 36.58 (S-CH-CO-), 58.41 (spiro-C), 115.45, 122.0 (C=C), 126.8, 127.01, 127.8, 128.68, 128.90, 129.1, 129.2, 129.89, 130.24, 131.49, 134.5, 137.19, 147.90 (N=C-S), 154.56 (C-N), 171.35 (C=O), 177.30 (C=O) (Found: C, 66.15; H, 4.62; N, 12.47; S, 10.68. Calcd. for $C_{49}H_{44}N_8O_3S_3$: C, 66.22; H, 4.95; N, 12.61; S, 10.81%).

Compound 9c: Yield (62%), m.p 165 °C; IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}): ν 3046, 2950, 1712 (C=O), 1690 (C=O), 1592 (C=C), 755 (C-S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 1.51–1.62 (8H, m, 4 $\times$ CH_2), 2.51–2.55 (4H, m, 2 $\times$ CH_2), 3.54 (2H, t, J 7.1 Hz, -CH- of the ring), 4.24 (4H, d, J 7.1 Hz, 2 $\times$ N- CH_2 -), 7.10–7.81 (25H, m, phenyl protons), 7.9 (1H, s, *exo*-olephenic proton); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 24.30, 27.52, 30.10, 36.33 (S-CH-CO-), 58.40 (spiro-C), 117.1, 122.5 (C=C), 126.25, 127.15, 127.77, 128.62, 128.90, 129.15, 129.2, 129.76, 130.19, 131.33, 134.5, 137.26, 148.60 (N=C-S), 169.4, 171.44 (C=O), 178.66 (C-O) (Found: C, 64.75; H, 4.52; N, 11.77; S, 10.08. Calcd. for $C_{51}H_{44}N_8O_5S_3$: C, 64.83; H, 4.66; N, 11.86; S, 10.17%).

The physical and analytical data of the compounds have been given in Table 1. However, their spectral data corroborate the proposed structures and depicted in Table 2.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	<i>n</i>	R	Mol. formulae	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
4a	1		$C_{38}H_{36}N_8O_2S_3$	168	75	62.10 (62.29)	4.73 (4.91)	15.10 (15.30)
4b	2		$C_{39}H_{38}N_8O_2S_3$	168	75	62.62 (62.73)	4.95 (5.09)	14.89 (15.01)

Table-1 (contd.)

4d	4		$C_{41}H_{42}N_8O_2S_3$	167	55	63.34 (63.57)	5.28 (5.42)	14.32 (14.47)
5a	1		$C_{40}H_{36}N_8O_4S_3$	165	74	60.56 (60.91)	4.35 (4.56)	13.98 (14.21)
5b	2		$C_{41}H_{38}N_8O_4S_3$	127	78	61.18 (61.35)	4.64 (4.73)	13.84 (13.96)
5d	4		$C_{43}H_{42}N_8O_4S_3$	125	60	61.91 (62.17)	4.80 (5.06)	13.30 (13.49)
6a	1		$C_{40}H_{36}N_8O_3S_3$	174	84	61.99 (62.18)	4.53 (4.66)	14.35 (14.51)
6b	2		$C_{41}H_{38}N_8O_3S_3$	168	68	62.46 (62.59)	4.68 (4.83)	14.17 (14.25)
6d	4		$C_{43}H_{42}N_8O_3S_3$	174	54	63.28 (63.39)	5.10 (5.16)	13.65 (13.76)
7a	1		$C_{42}H_{36}N_8O_5S_3$	172	61	60.67 (60.87)	4.20 (4.35)	13.39 (13.53)
7b	2		$C_{43}H_{38}N_8O_5S_3$	148	70	61.06 (61.28)	4.35 (4.51)	13.15 (13.30)
7d	4		$C_{45}H_{42}N_8O_5S_3$	174	51	62.96 (63.08)	4.81 (4.91)	12.93 (13.08)
8a	1		$C_{47}H_{40}N_8O_3S_3$	209	62	65.49 (65.58)	4.75 (4.65)	12.90 (13.02)
8b	2		$C_{48}H_{42}N_8O_3S_3$	208	61	65.78 (65.90)	4.75 (4.81)	12.73 (12.81)
8d	4		$C_{50}H_{46}N_8O_3S_3$	214	53	65.38 (66.52)	4.94 (5.10)	12.31 (12.42)
9a	1		$C_{49}H_{40}N_8O_5S_3$	151	65	64.02 (64.19)	4.28 (4.37)	12.10 (12.22)

Table-1 (contd.)

9b	2		$C_{50}H_{42}N_8O_5S_3$	150	65	64.32 (64.52)	4.36 (4.52)	11.89 (12.04)
9d	4		$C_{52}H_{46}N_8O_5S_3$	167	55	65.97 (66.10)	4.71 (4.87)	11.71 (11.86)

Table 2. Spectral data of synthesized compounds 4-9

Compd.	1H NMR	^{13}C NMR
4a	δ 1.58–1.64 (4H, m), 2.56–2.61 (4H, m), 3.90 (2H, t, 2 $\times$ S-CH-), 4.21 (4H, d, 2 $\times$ N-CH ₂ -), 6.8–7.2 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.3–7.8 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons), 8.46, 8.52 (2H, bs, 2 $\times$ NHCS)	δ 27.57, 30.35, 36.85, 48.40, 58.1, 127.8, 128.8, 129.2, 129.6, 130.23, 130.58, 134.5, 136.79, 154.90, 168.19, 171.30
4b	δ 1.59–1.65 (6H, m), 2.43–2.52 (4H, m), 3.84 (2H, t, S-CH-CO-), 4.26 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.7–7.0 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.1–7.5 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons), 8.42, 8.48 (2H, bs, 2 $\times$ NHCS)	δ 24.22, 27.48, 30.14, 36.83, 48.12, 57.80, 126.89, 127.1, 128.6, 129.12, 129.4, 130.26, 134.81, 137.10, 154.80, 167.23, 171.28
4d	δ 1.48–1.59 (10H, m), 2.52–2.62 (4H, m), 3.88 (2H, t, S-CH-CO-), 4.35 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 7.01–7.31 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.40–7.9 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons), 8.42, 8.48 (2H, bs, 2 $\times$ NHCS)	δ 23.60, 24.24, 27.51, 30.32, 36.81, 48.20, 58.38, 127.8, 128.8, 129.21, 129.42, 130.25, 130.60, 134.5, 137.19, 154.85, 168.1, 171.30
5a	δ 1.59–1.64 (4H, m), 2.56–2.65 (4H, m), 3.54 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.23 (4H, d, 2 $\times$ N-CH ₂ -), 6.85–7.28 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.34–7.82 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons), 8.45, 8.52 (2H, bs, 2 $\times$ NHCS)	δ 27.76, 30.87, 35.68, 48.69, 58.1, 127.8, 128.8, 129.2, 134.5, 169.3, 177.3
5b	δ 1.57–1.68 (6H, m), 2.45–2.59 (4H, m), 3.58 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.23 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.77–7.15 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.19–7.68 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons), 8.52, 8.68 (2H, bs, 2 $\times$ NHCS)	δ 24.34, 27.68, 30.32, 35.18, 48.40, 58.21, 127.8, 128.98, 129.2, 137.19, 168.80, 177.20
5d	δ 1.50–1.61 (10H, m), 2.51–2.60 (4H, m), 3.58 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.29 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.9–7.24 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.0–7.5 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons), 8.42, 8.48 (2H, bs, 2 $\times$ NHCS)	δ 23.58, 24.32, 27.48, 30.12, 35.15, 48.36, 58.66, 127.8, 128.8, 129.2, 137.19, 168.61, 177.33
6a	δ 1.63 (4H, m), 2.41 (4H, m), 3.75 (2H, t, CH-), 3.89 (2H, s, S-CH-CO-), 4.22 (4H, d, 2 $\times$ N-CH ₂ -), 6.9–7.3 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.42–7.9 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons)	δ 27.57, 30.71, 32.74, 36.90, 48.3, 58.1, 127.8, 128.8, 129.01, 129.2, 130.23, 132.15, 134.5, 137.19, 147.90, 154.8, 171.29, 173.58
6b	δ 1.53–1.60 (6H, m), 2.42–2.48 (4H, m), 3.65 (2H, s, S-CH ₂ -CO-), 3.90 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.26 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.9 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.0–7.5 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons)	δ 24.24, 27.48, 30.12, 32.70, 36.78, 48.20, 58.1, 127.8, 128.8, 129.1, 129.2, 130.16, 131.10, 134.5, 137.19, 147.90, 154.68, 170.60, 172.30
6d	δ 1.47–1.54 (10H, m), 2.54–2.66 (4H, m), 3.65 (2H, s, S-CH ₂ -CO-), 3.88 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.26 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.66–7.18 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.20–7.65 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons)	δ 23.58, 24.44, 27.56, 30.38, 32.80, 35.95, 48.49, 58.1, 127.18, 128.68, 129.18, 129.27, 130.32, 131.15, 134.45, 137.19, 147.90, 154.20, 170.80, 173.50

Table-2 (contd.)

7a	δ 1.62 (4H, m), 2.41 (4H, m), 3.51 (2H, t, 2 $\times$ S-CH-), 3.76 (2H, s, S-CH ₂ -CO-), 4.22 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.9-7.3 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.4-7.9 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons)	δ 26.90, 30.37, 32.78, 35.98, 48.4, 58.2, 127.8, 128.8, 129.2, 137.3, 147.90, 167.5, 171.30, 174.1
7b	δ 1.53-1.61 (6H, m), 2.44-2.53 (4H, m), 3.62 (2H, t, S-CH-), 3.72 (2H, s, S-CH ₂ -CO-), 4.29 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.64-6.68 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.10-7.56 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons)	δ 24.26, 27.48, 30.12, 32.74, 35.88, 48.45, 58.01, 127.8, 128.8, 129.3, 135.19, 147.90, 168.60, 171.93, 177.30
7d	δ 1.43-1.51 (10H, m), 2.54-2.65 (4H, m), 3.49 (2H, t, S-CH-), 3.69 (2H, s, S-CH ₂ -CO-), 4.23 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 6.9 (8H, m, <i>o</i> -phenyl protons), 7.0-7.5 (12H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons)	δ 23.58, 24.44, 27.56, 30.32, 32.75, 35.82, 48.38, 58.31, 127.8, 128.8, 129.2, 134.5, 147.90, 168.60, 171.32, 177.26
8a	δ 1.62 (4H, m), 2.31 (4H, m), 3.63 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.20 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 7.29-7.95 (25H, m, phenyl protons), 8.20 (1H, s, thiozolidinone C=CH-)	δ 27.67, 30.87, 36.78, 48.35, 58.41, 115.21, 122.3, 126.68, 127.30, 127.8, 128.65, 128.8, 129.05, 129.2, 130.01, 130.31, 134.34, 135.7, 136.8, 148.60, 155.01, 172.01, 174.5
8b	δ 1.58-1.61 (6H, m), 2.52-1.56 (4H, m), 3.65 (2H, s, S-CH ₂ -CO-), 3.83 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.26 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 7.18-7.85 (25H, m, phenyl protons), 8.10 (1H, s, thiozolidinone C=CH-)	δ 24.26, 27.48, 30.12, 36.65, 48.35, 58.31, 115.53, 122.49, 126.34, 127.58, 127.8, 128.8, 129.31, 129.69, 134.5, 135.6, 137.19, 147.90, 154.30, 170.30, 173.30
8d	δ 1.43-1.51 (12H, m), 2.53-2.62 (4H, m), 3.83 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.36 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 7.28-7.95 (25H, m, phenyl protons), 8.27 (1H, s, thiozolidinone C=CH-)	δ 23.58, 24.44, 27.56, 30.32, 36.91, 48.30, 58.20, 115.36, 122.61, 126.38, 127.55, 127.8, 128.46, 128.78, 129.1, 129.2, 130.56, 131.46, 132.56, 134.5, 137.19, 147.45, 154.60, 171.32, 177.30
9a	δ 1.60-1.65 (4H, m), 2.58-2.64 (4H, m), 3.66 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.19 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 7.23-7.88 (25H, m, <i>m,p</i> -phenyl protons), 8.12 (1H, s, thiozolidinone C=CH-)	δ 27.48, 30.32, 35.45, 48.43, 58.25, 115.53, 122.6, 126.67, 127.8, 128.8, 129.1, 129.2, 131.5, 135.35, 137.19, 147.90, 168.21, 172.12, 177.30
9b	δ 1.55-1.60 (6H, m), 2.54-2.59 (4H, m), 3.68 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.37 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 7.32-7.9 (25H, m, phenyl protons), 8.08 (thiozolidinone C=CH-)	δ 24.24, 27.38, 30.12, 35.08, 48.47, 58.29, 115.32, 122.52, 127.8, 128.8, 129.1, 129.2, 130.10, 131.01, 134.5, 137.19, 147.81, 168.10, 174.10, 177.45
9d	δ 1.43-1.50 (10H, m), 2.51-2.56 (4H, m), 3.61 (2H, t, S-CH-), 4.20 (4H, d, N-CH ₂ -), 7.10-7.73 (25H, m, phenyl protons), 8.02 (1H, s, thiozolidinone C=CH-)	δ 23.58, 24.44, 27.56, 30.38, 35.28, 48.34, 58.28, 115.34, 122.8, 126.23, 127.8, 128.8, 129.10, 129.2, 130.01, 134.5, 137.19, 147.90, 168.60, 173.85, 177.30

Antimicrobial activities :

All the newly prepared Mannich bases were screened for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cirroflagellosus* using Norfloxacin as standard and their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* using Griseofulvin as standard. Dimethylformamide was used as a solvent control. The culture media was nutrient agar

and the method employed was cup-plate method²⁶. The zones of inhibition formed were measured in mm and are represented by (+), (++) and (+++) depending upon the diameter and clarity. Norfloxacin showed a zone of inhibition of 28 mm against *E. coli* and 25 mm against *Bacillus cirroflagellosus*. Griseofulvin exhibited a zone of inhibition of 25 mm against the fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*. All the compounds screened were

Table 3. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of the compounds 4-9

Compd.	Zone of inhibition				
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus cirroflagellosus</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
4a	++	+++	+	+	++
4b	+	+	+	++	+++
4c	+++	++	+++	++	+
4d	++	++	+	++	++
5a	++	+++	++	+	+
5b	++	++	+	++	+
5c	+	++	++	++	+
5d	++	+	+	+	++
6a	+	++	+	+	+
6b	++	+++	++	++	+
6c	++	++	+	++	+
6d	++	++	+	++	++
7a	++	++	+	+	++
7b	++	+++	++	+	+
7c	++	++	++	+	+
7d	++	+	+	++	++
8a	+	++	+	++	+
8b	++	+	++	+	++
8c	++	++	++	+	+
8d	+	++	++	++	+
9a	++	+++	++	+++	+
9b	++	++	+	++	++
9c	++	+	+	++	++
9d	+	++	+	++	+

Notes : (+) = weakly active (12-16 mm); (++) = moderately active (17-21 mm); (+++) = highly active (22-30 mm).

found to exhibit weak or moderate antibacterial and antifungal activities (zone of inhibition 12 to 16 mm or 17 to 21 mm) which are shown in Table 3.

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